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POLICY ON SPORTS IN THE SOCIETY IMPLEMENTATION AND ITS MODERN CONDITIONS

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Annotation: *In this article, along with the analysis of reforms in the field of physical culture and sports in the new Uzbekistan, the existing problems in the field, in particular, the involvement of the general population in sports and healthy lifestyles, raising a physically healthy generation, the relevance of the organization of large-scale work on the implementation of conceptual programs for the development of the sports industry and infrastructure, the promotion of physical culture and sports among young people.*

Keywords: *New Uzbekistan, sports policy, social policy, measures, physical culture and sports, youth activity, program*

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been taking consistent measures to promote physical culture and sports, promote a healthy lifestyle, create the necessary conditions for the physical rehabilitation of people with disabilities and ensure the proper participation of domestic athletes in international sports arenas.

It is no secret that the development of physical culture and sports, the promotion of public health, the development of domestic and foreign policy of society and its place in the world through the promotion of our country in the international arena.

We can see the urgency of this issue from the words of the President of our country Sh.M.Mirziyoyev: "Deciding on a healthy lifestyle in society, further popularization of physical culture and sports are among our urgent tasks"[1].

In this sense, in the field of physical culture and sports, members of society, specific measures to promote the health of the general population, the implementation of programs, the broad involvement of the younger generation in sports and the selection of talented athletes, The need to form national teams with athletes and create additional conditions for their coaches is growing from year to year.

In this regard, in order to form a comprehensively mature and physically healthy citizen with a high culture in the country, to identify priorities for improving the skills and knowledge of the population in the field of physical culture and sports, to introduce

innovative forms and methods of selection of talented athletes. On January 24, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" will be adopted.

On the basis of this Decree to increase the total number of people regularly engaged in physical culture and sports to 30%, the total number of young people engaged in sports organizations and institutions to 20%; Gradually increase the quality of coaches and specialists in public sports education institutions, in particular, the number of employees with higher education to 80%; Development and implementation of an effective and transparent four-stage system of selection (selection) of talented athletes among young people – organization-district (city) –region-republic[2].

In addition, the document provides for the development of sports tourism in the field of sports from 2020 through the systematic holding of the international marathon "Tashkent Marathon", the international eco-marathon "Save Aral", motor rally and motocross; introduction of "Physical fitness level" tests among all segments of the population; establishment of complex scientific laboratories for athletes of national teams in sports, the introduction of advanced innovative technologies in the training process and the establishment of effective medical and pharmacological support in the field of sports; Introduce a mechanism for regular in-depth medical examination of members of the regional national team in sports under 18 years of age in the youth departments of regional children's multidisciplinary medical centers and older regional team members in district (city) multidisciplinary central polyclinics; creation of infrastructure for winter Olympic sports, establishment of a system of training professional athletes through the popularization of these sports; Establishment of the Olympic Training Center in Bostanlyk district, Tashkent region, for the systematic preparation of Uzbek sports delegations for prestigious sports competitions; establishment of "hospital services" in order to attract foreign athletes and fans and the effective use of sports infrastructure, the introduction of additional (non-electronic) entry visa "Sport Visa"; identification of necessary measures to increase the participation of the private sector in sports, including reducing the share of the state in sports organizations; Establishment of optional classes and clubs on sports included in the program "Army Games" for students of law enforcement agencies and educational institutions of the Armed Forces, including the "Temurbek School"; Wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the management system of physical culture and sports, sports facilities and institutions, including ensuring the connection of sports facilities to the telecommunications network through the information system "Sport.uz"; the implementation of systemic measures to develop and

increase the popularity of national sports, their inclusion in the programs of the Asian and Olympic Games.[3]

It is no coincidence that the above tasks and tasks need to be identified, because the problems that have accumulated over the years in the field of sports, the need for the widespread introduction of modern sports in society, the demand is growing day by day.

In particular, the existence of a number of systemic problems and shortcomings in the organization of physical culture and sports hinders the effective implementation of state policy in this area and the full use of the country's existing sports potential. These can be substantiated as follows:

- The lack of an effective integrated system of physical culture and sports management in the field does not fully ensure the proper coordination of the activities of government agencies and other organizations in this area, the promotion and promotion of a healthy lifestyle;

- There was a need for the concept of development of physical culture and sports in the medium and long term in our country, defining specific tasks and targets in the field of both mass sports and higher sports achievements;

- Lack of interaction with the non-governmental sector on the creation of modern material and technical base and infrastructure of sports in the context of public-private partnership does not allow to effectively address the existing problems in this area;

- Lack of an effective and transparent system of selection of talented athletes among young people on the ground hinders the formation of sports reserves for the quality of the national team and the training of highly qualified athletes;

- The current system of training, retraining and advanced training of sports personnel, especially management staff, does not meet the needs of qualified specialists in the field of physical culture and sports management;

- Innovative research and methodological developments in the training of athletes and their medical care, the lack of standards that meet modern requirements do not adequately ensure the quality of the training process;

- It can be said that the production of quality local sports equipment and inventory that meets international standards is not widely established, nor is there an effective mechanism to support such production.[4]

In addition, today it is necessary to cover all segments of the population with physical culture and mass sports, to actively promote the importance of physical culture and mass sports in human and family life, its physical and mental health and maturity. issues such as creating the necessary conditions for the realization of their talents, the selection of special talents in the field of sports and improving the system of targeted

training are waiting for a systematic solution. The material and technical base of a number of sports facilities does not meet modern requirements, the level of effective use of sports facilities remains low.

In order to address the accumulated problems in this area, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures to further develop physical culture and mass sports." [5]

This resolution approved the program for further development of physical culture and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with which it is planned to carry out large-scale, targeted work. Including according to the program:

further improvement of legislation aimed at developing the system of organization and management of physical culture and sports;

strengthening the material and technical base of physical culture and sports, construction of modern sports complexes, equipping them with modern sports equipment and facilities, development of the private sector in this area;

scientific and methodological support of training, retraining and advanced training institutions in the field of physical culture and sports, providing sports schools with highly qualified coaches and medical staff;

It is planned to take comprehensive measures to improve the health of schoolchildren and students, the general population, the organization of mass sports, the organization of complex sports competitions, the selection of talented athletes from among young people and their targeted training.

Within the framework of the program, the introduction of the position of "Athlete" in the staff of the Republican schools of higher sports and children and youth sports will be an important step towards further strengthening the system of financial support for members of national teams of Uzbekistan [6].

In addition, in order to radically improve the system of public administration in the field of physical culture and sports, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially youth, as well as the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, new and long-term programs and projects are being developed.

In particular, in order to form a comprehensively mature and physically healthy person with a high culture in our society, to set priorities for improving the skills and knowledge of the population in the field of physical culture and sports, to introduce innovative forms and methods of selection of talented athletes. In January 2013, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and

sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved the concept of development of physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025.

On the basis of this concept, in order to select young athletes and establish a system of formation of sports reserves, to achieve high results in the promotion of sports among young people, based on the specifics of the regions, the interests and aspirations of the population, secondary schools institutions specialize in at least one priority, prospective, emerging, including national sports[7].

In addition, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of public administration in tourism, sports and cultural heritage"[8] and the Resolution "On the organization of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports"[9] The ministry was established. In particular, the Decree "On measures to further improve the system of public administration in the field of tourism, sports and cultural heritage" was signed.

According to the document, the following will be organized:

- Ministry of Tourism and Sports on the basis of the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports and the State Committee for Tourism Development;
- On the basis of the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports and the relevant territorial subdivisions of the State Committee for Tourism Development, the main departments of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, districts (cities);
- The Department of Cultural Heritage under the Ministry of Culture, its Departments of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent and the Agency for Cultural Heritage under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its departments of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent.

Established ministry:

- is a public administration body implementing a unified state policy in the field of tourism, physical culture, sports and cultural heritage, and the Ministry of Tourism and Sports is the legal successor to the rights, obligations and agreements of the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports and the State Committee for Tourism Development;
- has the right to adopt normative legal acts that are universally binding within its competence.

The main tasks and activities of the Ministry are:

- b) in the field of physical culture and sports:
 - Effective management of sports facilities on the basis of PPP and the introduction of modern information technology in this area;

- Implement a unified policy aimed at involving the general population in sports and a healthy lifestyle, educating a physically healthy younger generation, developing the sports industry and infrastructure, ensuring the country's worthy participation in the international sports arena in the field of high sportsmanship;

- Coordination of the activities of ministries and departments of physical culture and sports societies and clubs, sports federations (associations), etc.[10]

There is another side of the issue, and when it comes to the attention paid to sports in society, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issue of training institutions and specialists in this area.

In the system of retraining and advanced training of specialists in physical culture and sports, taking into account the specifics of the activities of sports specialists in the Center for scientific and methodological support, retraining and advanced training of specialists in physical culture and sports under the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan it is advisable to teach the basics of knowledge, more broadly, of course.

It is necessary to strive to increase the professional training of specialists in physical education and sports in the training of various categories of staff. Let them have legal knowledge in a way that they can apply wisely in their activities. Requirements and qualifications for the heads of sports educational institutions and their subdivisions should, first of all, provide the necessary level of legal knowledge of human rights and freedoms[11].

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 14, 2018 No PP-3907 "On measures to bring up young people spiritually, morally and physically harmoniously, to raise their education system to a qualitatively new level"[12] and the state "Youth is our future" The program reflected the issue of creating conditions for regular physical culture and sports among young people, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among them.

In recent years, much has been done to promote physical culture and mass sports among the population. "Health corridors" and sports grounds have been built in the mahallas, sports clubs have been opened in educational institutions, and boarding schools have been opened. As a result, the attitude of our people to their own health has changed radically.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2020 "On measures for the widespread implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" in the conditions of the past pandemic, played a significant role in the test days. A healthy lifestyle combined with physical education and sports. On

the basis of this Decree, the work started in our country on a healthy lifestyle, measures to promote mass sports are developing at a new stage, creating opportunities for the population to play sports in school gyms.

In recent years, sports in the new Uzbekistan have reached the level of politics. Over the past 4 years, more than a dozen decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on physical culture and sports, about 100 normative legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers have been adopted. On their basis, the field of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan is leading to a radical renewal.[13]

For example, at the Summer Olympic Games in Tokyo, Japan, from July 23 to August 8, 2021, which were postponed for a year due to a coronavirus pandemic, the final lineup of athletes announced by the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan took deserved places. In addition, our athletes, who have defended the honor of our country in these competitions and achieved great success in many prestigious international competitions, in particular, showed high courage and perseverance at the XVI Summer Paralympic Games in Tokyo, Japan. His significant contribution to the glory of the country and the award of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for effective and exemplary work in educating the younger generation in the spirit of national pride and patriotism are an example of the attention paid to sports in our country.[14] The head of our state said: “Today, modern and easy-to-use sports infrastructure is being built in all regions of the country, including the most remote districts. Over the past two years, the number of people regularly involved in sports in our country has doubled. Athletes of our country have won more than a thousand medals at various international competitions, of which more than 400 are gold medals. At present, the schools formed in Uzbekistan in boxing, judo, freestyle wrestling, rhythmic gymnastics, weightlifting, chess and other sports are known all over the world.”[15]

Thus, the above-mentioned problems need to be addressed, in particular, the definition of specific tasks and targets in the field of public and higher sports achievements in society, the development of measures for the long-term development of physical culture and sports. – Achieve short-term prospects by creating a technical base and infrastructure, forming a sports reserve and training highly qualified athletes, meeting the need for qualified specialists in the field of physical culture and sports management, launching the production of quality sports equipment and inventory that meets international standards is achieved and adherence to the concept of the field finds its proof.

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